

Training scientists on RDM

Software

Development Best Practices

...principles of Clean Code and professional Git usage.

Containers

... for use with Docker, Apptainer and Compute4PUNCH.

JupyterHub

... packages integrated into Jupyter Notebook, providing hands-on training environment.

Infrastructure

... like REANA, Compute4PUNCH and Storage4PUNCH.

Fact sheet

- Trainings are organised by the PUNCH4NFDI Young Academy (PYA)
 - A list of trainings is available under <https://indico.desy.de/category/1057/>
- Information and support is also provided by the PUNCH4NFDI helpdesk, send an email to support@punch4nfdi.de
- Further training offers or workshops, especially on general Research Data Management topics, are available on NFDI level.

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